

Original Research Article

Outcome of Visual Internal Urethrotomy in Comparison with Anastomotic Urethroplasty for Short Segment Bulbar Urethral Stricture

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Abstract: Objective: This study was conducted to compare the outcome between optical internal urethrotomy and end to end urethroplasty in patients with short segment bulbar urethral stricture up to 1.5 cm. **Methods:** This comparative purposive sampling study was conducted in the Department of Urology, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University over a period from January 2014 to December 2014. A total of 50 patients with short-segment (≤ 1.5 cm) bulbar urethral strictures were consecutively included in the study (25 patients in each group). Student's t-test and chi-square test were applied for hypothesis testing. 'P' value < 0.05 was considered as significant. **Results:** About 20% of patients in OI Urethrotomy group experienced bleeding and another 4% incontinence. In contrast, 6% of patients in Anastomotic Urethroplasty group complained of periurethral leakage, 8% fever and another 8% wound infection. Six (24%) of patients in OI Urethrotomy Group developed narrow urinary stream at month 3, as opposed to none in Anastomotic Urethroplasty Group ($p = 0.001$). Nearly 30% of patients in OI Urethrotomy Group had narrow urinary stream at month 6 compared 4% in Anastomotic Urethroplasty Group ($p = 0.024$). The recurrence rate of stricture in OI Urethrotomy was 24% (6 out of 25 patients) at month 3. However, none in Anastomotic Urethroplasty Group had history of recurrence of stricture ($p = 0.011$). At baseline the mean uroflowmetry was 5.5 ml/sec in both groups which immediately increased to 25.3 ± 2.6 ml/sec and 23.9 ± 2.2 ml/sec in OI urethrotomy and Anastomotic Urethroplasty groups respectively and then dropped to 18.4 ± 6.3 ml/sec and 20.2 ± 2.6 ml/sec in OI Urethrotomy and Anastomotic Urethroplasty groups respectively at month 3 and to 17.8 ± 6.4 ml/second and 19.6 ± 2.6 ml/sec respectively at month 6. **Conclusion:** The study concluded that anastomotic urethroplasty was an effective and satisfactory technique for the treatment of short segment bulbar urethral stricture. The morbidity and complications were low and outcomes were excellent.

Keywords: Stricture urethra, Optical Internal Urethrotomy (OI Urethrotomy), Anastomotic Urethroplasty.

INTRODUCTION

Urethral stricture is the narrowing of the caliber of the urethra caused by the presence of a scar mostly consequence of infection or injury. It is one of the common urological problems. The term urethral stricture refers to anterior urethral disease or a scarring process involving the spongy erectile tissue of the corpus spongiosum. The spongy erectile tissue of the corpus spongiosum underlies the urethral epithelium and in some cases the scarring process extend through the tissue of the corpus spongiosum and into adjacent tissue. Contraction of this scar reduces the urethral lumen [7].

Stricture disease can have profound impact on quality of life. It may lead to urinary tract infection, bladder calculi, urethrocutaneous fistula, sepsis and renal failure. Urethral stricture disease is a common urological and is one of the most important causes of bladder outflow obstruction which may be resulted from varieties of pathology e.g. inflammatory disease, injuries of urethra, urethral neoplasm etc [1]. In the management of urethral strictures the etiology, site, length of stricture are taken into account. Peterson and Webster suggested that no one technique is appropriate for all stricture diseases and the urologist must be familiar with various surgical

techniques to deal with any condition of the urethra during surgery. Surgical treatment of urethral strictures includes numerous options such as dilatation, optical internal urethrotomy, stent and reconstructive surgical techniques [2]. Urethroplasty is an open surgical procedure for urethral reconstruction to treat urethral strictures. Urethroplasty can be performed by two methods; primary repair which involves complete excision of the narrowed part of urethra. The proximal and distal patent parts are then rejoined. The second method of urethroplasty utilizes tissue transfer or free graft technique. The gold standard treatment of a short segment bulbar stricture is excision, spatulation of the two ends and an overlapping end to end anastomosis, whether or not the lumen is completely occluded. Internal urethrotomy refers any procedure that opens the stricture by incising or ablating it transurethrally. The urethrotomy procedure involves incising scar upto healthy tissue to allow the scar to expand (release of scar contracture and the lumen to heal). Optical internal urethrotomy continue to be the most commonly used techniques, but have a high recurrence rate and many patients progress to surgical repair. Moreover, optical internal urethrotomy exacerbates scar formation, thus adding to stricture length and predisposing difficult definitive open repair and a lower success rate [4]. Several studies have been conducted in different parts of the world comparing the safety and efficacy between anastomotic urethroplasty and optical internal urethrotomy in short segment bulbar urethral stricture treatment. Urethral mucosa has several unique characteristics that make it superior to any tissues for reconstruction of urethra. Open urethroplasty is regarded as the gold standard treatment for urethral strictures [3]. In Bangladesh continuous debate has been going on among urologist about the first & logical treatment option in treating short- segment bulbar urethral stricture. This study was conducted to compare the outcome of anastomotic urethroplasty with that of traditional optical internal urethrotomy in the treatment of short-segment bulbar urethral stricture. Patients and methods: The comparative clinical study was conducted in the Department of Urology, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University over a period from January 2014 to

December 2014. A total of 50 patients with short-segment (≤ 1.5 cm) bulbar urethral strictures were consecutively included in the study (25 patients in each group). The required numbers of patients were consecutively included in the study and were randomly assigned either optical internal urethrotomy or anastomotic urethroplasty groups. The present study has been conducted on the patients with bulbar urethral stricture size ≤ 1.5 cm , age ranging from 15 to 50 years and no other co-existing diseases e.g. ESRD, BXO, active infection, immune-compromise, malignant stricture urethra or history of PUDD, were admitted for anastomotic urethroplasty & OIU fulfilling the selection criteria. Preoperatively, both retrograde urethrography, micturating cystourethrography and ultrasonography was used to evaluate the location, length and density of the stricture. All patients were evaluated by history, physical examination and some investigations including urine analysis & cultural sensitivity (C/S), serum creatinine, random blood sugar (RBS) and uroflowmetry. Patients with documented urinary tract infection (UTI) were treated with appropriate antibiotics before the procedure & confirmed by repeat culture sensitivity (C/S). The surgical procedure was performed with the patients under spinal anesthesia. All patients were followed-up by urinary symptoms, uroflowmetry, urine analysis, RGU & MCU at 3 and 6 months. Data were processed and analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). The test statistics used to analyze the data were descriptive statistics, Fisher Exact Probability Test and Student's t-Test. For all analytical tests, the level of significance was set at 0.05 and $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

RESULTS

Twenty percent of patients in OI Urethrotomy group experienced bleeding, 4% epididymitis and another 4% incontinence. In contrast, 8% of patients in Anastomotic Urethroplasty group complained of periurethral leakage, 8% fever and another 8% wound infection. (Table I). Fisher Exact Test was done to analyze the data. Table I Comparison of complications between groups following intervention.

Table I: Comparison of Postoperative Complications between OI Urethrotomy and Anastomotic Urethroplasty

Complications	OI Urethrotomy (n=25)	Anastomotic Urethroplasty (n=25)	P-Value
Periurethral leakage	00	2(8.0%)	0.245
Bleeding	5(20.0%)	00	0.011
Fever	00	2(8.0%)	0.245
Epididymitis	1(4.0%)	00	0.500
Incontinence	1(4.0%)	00	0.500
Wound infection	00	2(8.0%)	0.245

Six (24%) of patients in OI Urethrotomy Group exhibited narrow urinary stream at month 3, as opposed to none in Anastomotic Urethroplasty Group ($p = 0.001$). Nearly 30% of patients in OI Urethrotomy Group had narrow urinary stream at month 6 compared 4% in

Anastomotic Urethroplasty Group. The difference was statistically significant in terms of narrow urinary stream ($p = 0.024$) (Table II). Fisher Exact test was done to analyze the data.

Table II: Comparison of Narrow Urinary Stream between Groups

Follow up	OI Urethrotomy (n=25)	Anastomotic Urethroplasty (n=25)	P-Value
Narrow urinary stream at 3 months	6(24%)	00	0.011
Narrow urinary stream at 6 months	7(28%)	1(4%)	0.024

Of the 25 patients in OI Urethrotomy Group, 1(4%) developed UTI at 3 month and 5(20%) at 6 months. None of the patients in Anastomotic Urethroplasty Group developed UTI. There was

significant difference between groups in terms of UTI at 6 month ($p = 0.025$) (Table III). Fisher Exact Test was done to analyze the data.

Table III: Comparison of UTI between Groups

Follow up	OI Urethrotomy (n=25)	Anastomotic Urethrotomy (n=25)	P-Value
UTI at 3 months	1(4%)	00	0.500
UTI at 6 months	5(20%)	00	0.025

The recurrence rate of stricture in OI Urethrotomy was 24% (6 out of 25 patients) at 3 months. However, none in Anastomotic Urethroplasty Group had history of recurrence of stricture. Seven (28.1%) patients in OI Urethrotomy needed a second urethrotomy, where as only 1(4%) required Anastomotic urethroplasty at 6

months. The differences between the groups in terms of recurrence of stricture at 3 month and at 6 months were statistically significant ($p = 0.011$ and $p = 0.024$ respectively) (Table IV). Fisher Exact Test was done to analyze the data.

Table IV: Comparison of Recurrence of Stricture between Groups (n = 50)

Follow up	OI Urethrotomy (n=25)	Anastomotic Urethroplasty (n=25)	P-Value
Recurrence of stricture at month 3	6(24%)	00	0.011
Recurrence of stricture at month 6	7(28.1%)	1(4%)	0.024

Table V shows the comparison of changes in mean uroflowmetry between groups at different time intervals. At baseline the mean uroflowmetry was 5.5 ± 2.6 ml/sec in both groups which immediately increased to 25.3 ± 2.6 ml/sec and 23.9 ± 2.2 ml/sec in OI urethrotomy and Anastomotic Urethroplasty groups respectively and then dropped to 18.4 ± 6.3 ml/sec and 20.2 ± 2.6 ml/sec in OI Urethrotomy and Anastomotic

Urethroplasty groups respectively at 3 month and to 17.8 ± 6.4 ml/sec and 19.6 ± 2.6 ml/sec respectively at 6 months. The uroflowmetry improved in both groups compared to their baseline figures, but no significant difference was between the groups with respect to improvement. Data were analyzed using Student's t-Test and were presented as mean \pm SD.

Table V: Uroflowmetry at Different Time Interval between Groups (n = 50)

Uroflowmetry (ml/sec)	OI Urethrotomy (n=25)	Anastomotic Urethroplasty (n=25)	P-Value
At baseline	5.5 ± 1.7	5.5 ± 1.8	0.936
Immediate outcome	25.3 ± 2.6	23.9 ± 2.2	0.039
Follow up at month 3	18.4 ± 6.3	20.2 ± 2.6	0.217
Follow up at month 6	17.8 ± 6.4	19.6 ± 2.6	0.218

DISCUSSION

This study was designed to evaluate the outcome of optical internal urethrotomy (OIU) and anastomotic urethroplasty in the treatment of short segment bulbar urethral stricture. Andrich et al. (2003) stated that the result of anastomotic urethroplasty was good and sustained in the long term, while the result of OIU deteriorated steadily with time. An anastomotic repair should be performed in presence to an optical internal urethrotomy when possible [5]. Primary end-to-end anastomosis was the gold standard reconstructive technique for short segment bulbar stricture urethra (<2

cm), with free graft and pedicle flaps best reserved for longer strictures [8]. In OIU group, inflammatory stricture was found in 52% of cases, traumatic stricture in 20%, iatrogenic in 12% and idiopathic in 16% of cases; while in anastomotic urethroplasty group inflammatory stricture was in 60%, traumatic in 16%, iatrogenic in 16% and idiopathic in 8% of cases. Immediate outcome of intervention shows that 20% of patients in optical internal urethrotomy (OIU) group encountered bleeding, 4% developed epididymitis and another 4% incontinence of urine. In contrast, 6% of patients in anastomotic urethroplasty group had

periurethral leakage, 8% fever and another 8% wound infection. All the complications except bleeding were almost identically distributed between groups. Stormont *et al.* (1993) reported that all the complications except bleeding were nearly identical between optical internal urethrotomy (OIU) and anastomotic urethroplasty [9]. Nearly one-quarter (24%) of patients in optical internal urethrotomy (OIU) Group exhibited poor urinary stream at month 3, as opposed to none in anastomotic urethroplasty Group. Narrow urinary stream at month 6 demonstrated its significant presence in Optical internal urethrotomy (OIU) Group (30%) compared to that in anastomotic urethroplasty Group (4%) ($p < 0.05$). The recurrence of stricture in optical internal urethrotomy at month 3 was 24% as opposed to none in anastomotic urethroplasty Group ($p = 0.011$). Seven (28.1%) patients in optical internal urethrotomy (OIU) needed a second urethrotomy, whereas only 1(4%) required anastomotic urethroplasty at 6th month ($p = 0.024$). Albers *et al.* (1996) demonstrated in their study a recurrence rate of 44.8% after primary urethrotomy and 34.6% underwent a second urethrotomy. The recurrence rate of anastomotic urethroplasty was 26.9% and 16.9% needed a second urethroplasty [10]. The mean uroflowmetry at baseline was 5.5 ml/sec in both groups which steeply increased in both optical internal urethrotomy (OIU) and anastomotic urethroplasty groups reaching a mean uroflowmetry of 25.3 ± 2.6 ml/ sec and 23.9 ± 2.2 ml/sec respectively and then dropped to 18.4 ± 6.3 ml/sec and 20.2 ± 2.6 ml/sec in optical internal urethrotomy (OIU) and anastomotic urethroplasty groups respectively at month 3 and to 17.8 ± 6.4 ml/sec and 19.6 ± 2.6 ml/sec respectively at month 6. Kane *et al.* (2002) reported in his study that average peak urinary flow rates increased from 7.9 ml/sec at baseline to 30.1 ml/sec postoperatively in anastomotic group [11].

CONCLUSION

From the findings of the study and discussion thereof, it can be concluded that anastomotic urethroplasty is a versatile, effective and a satisfactory technique for the treatment of short segment bulbar urethral strictures. The morbidity and complications are low and outcomes are excellent.

Conflict of Interest: None

Abbreviations

- UTI: Urinary tract infection
- RGU: Retrograde urethrogram

- MCU: Micturating urethrogram
- OIU: Optical internal urethrotomy

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